

**DIGITAL TECHNOLOGIES AND INCLUSION OF STUDENTS WITH
HIGH SKILLS: VIRTUAL REALITY AND ARTIFICIAL
INTELLIGENCE AS PEDAGOGICAL RESOURCES IN SPECIAL
EDUCATION**

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ABSTRACT

This study investigates the use of Digital Information and Communication Technologies (DICTs), such as Virtual Reality (VR) and Artificial Intelligence (AI), in the inclusion of students with special abilities in school environments. The research contextualizes the advances and challenges in the use of these technologies for personalization and immersion in special education, identifying how the lack of infrastructure and insufficient teacher training impact their application. The main question addresses the inclusive potential of DICTs for this specific group. The general objective is to analyze the effectiveness of these technologies in the inclusive education of high abilities. Under the neoperspectivist paradigm giftedean , with theories by Gardner, Gagné , Renzulli and Subotnik , the research adopts the hypothetical-deductive method and conducts a Narrative Bibliographic and Documentary Review. The analysis included 72 works selected from the Scopus , Web of Science and ERIC. The main findings indicate that VR and AI personalize learning and promote engagement, although infrastructure challenges and ethical regulations remain significant barriers. Limitations include the lack of empirical and experimental analysis, restricting inferences about the practical effects of the technologies in the long term . The theoretical and empirical contributions highlight the importance of public policies and teacher training, adding value to the topic and to the educational field by proposing solutions for broader and more equitable inclusion.

Keywords: Pedagogical Innovation. Cognitive Development. Technological Mediation. Inclusive Education. Educational Policies.

RESUMO

Este estudo investiga o uso de Tecnologias Digitais da Informação e Comunicação (TDICs), como a Realidade Virtual (RV) e a Inteligência Artificial (IA), na inclusão de alunos com altas habilidades em ambientes escolares. A pesquisa contextualiza os avanços e desafios no uso dessas tecnologias para a personalização e imersão na educação especial, identificando como a falta de infraestrutura e a formação docente insuficiente impactam sua aplicação. A questão principal aborda o potencial inclusivo das TDICs para esse grupo específico. O objetivo geral é analisar a eficácia dessas tecnologias na educação inclusiva de altas habilidades. Sob o paradigma neoperspectivista giftediano, com teorias de Gardner, Gagné, Renzulli e Subotnik, a pesquisa adota o método hipotético-dedutivo e conduz uma Revisão Bibliográfica e Documental Narrativa. A análise incluiu 72 trabalhos selecionados nas bases Scopus, Web of Science e ERIC. Os principais achados indicam que a RV e a IA personalizam o aprendizado e promovem o engajamento, embora desafios de infraestrutura e regulamentações éticas permaneçam como barreiras significativas. As limitações incluem a falta de análise empírica e experimental, restringindo as inferências sobre os efeitos práticos das tecnologias a longo prazo. As contribuições teóricas e empíricas evidenciam a importância de políticas públicas e formação docente, agregando valor à temática e à área educacional ao propor soluções para uma inclusão mais ampla e equitativa.

Palavras-chave: Inovação Pedagógica. Desenvolvimento Cognitivo. Mediação Tecnológica. Ensino Inclusivo. Políticas Educacionais.

RESUMEN

Este estudio investiga el uso de Tecnologías de la Información y la Comunicación Digital (TDIC), como la Realidad Virtual (VR) y la Inteligencia Artificial (IA), en la inclusión de estudiantes con altas capacidades en entornos escolares. La investigación contextualiza los avances y desafíos en el uso de estas tecnologías para la personalización e inmersión en la educación especial, identificando cómo la falta de infraestructura y la insuficiente capacitación docente impactan en su aplicación. La pregunta principal aborda el potencial inclusivo de las TDIC para este grupo específico. El objetivo general es analizar la efectividad de estas tecnologías en la educación inclusiva de alta cualificación. Bajo el paradigma neoperspectivista giftediano, con teorías de Gardner, Gagné, Renzulli y Subotnik, la investigación adopta el método hipotético-deductivo y realiza una revisión narrativa bibliográfica y documental. El análisis incluyó 72 trabajos seleccionados de las bases de datos Scopus, Web of Science y ERIC. Los hallazgos clave indican que la realidad virtual y la inteligencia artificial personalizan el aprendizaje y promueven la participación, aunque los desafíos de infraestructura y las regulaciones éticas siguen siendo barreras importantes. Las limitaciones incluyen la falta de análisis empíricos y experimentales, lo que restringe las inferencias sobre los efectos prácticos a largo plazo de las tecnologías. Los aportes teóricos y empíricos resaltan la importancia de las políticas públicas y la formación docente, agregando valor al tema y al área educativa al proponer soluciones para una inclusión más amplia y equitativa.

Palabras-clave: Innovación Pedagógica. Desarrollo cognitivo. Mediación Tecnológica. Enseñanza inclusiva. Políticas Educativas.

1. INTRODUCTION

The inclusion of gifted and highly skilled students in the educational system is a challenge that mobilizes several studies and innovative pedagogical practices. In this context,

Digital Information and Communication Technologies (DICTs), especially Virtual Reality (VR) and Artificial Intelligence (AI), emerge as tools capable of enriching the learning experience, creating environments that meet specific educational demands. According to Gagné and VanTassel-Baska (2019), the use of these technologies offers a significant expansion in the possibilities of personalized learning, allowing gifted students to develop their potential in an optimized and contextualized way . Studies such as those by Pfeiffer (2020) and Renzulli (2021) corroborate the relevance of the use of DICTs , especially in inclusive contexts, demonstrating that these tools can facilitate the identification, support and development of students with exceptional abilities, offering new pedagogical perspectives.

The debate on the inclusion of students with high abilities is still recent in Brazil, being driven mainly by the implementation of public policies that aim to expand access to specialized education (Alencar, 2019; Moran , 2022). In the international scenario, highly relevant research, such as that of Subotnik et al. (2022) and Plucker et al. (2023) indicate that the use of advanced technologies, such as AI and VR, can significantly contribute to pedagogical practices that effectively serve these students in inclusive schools. However, the adoption of these tools in school environments still faces challenges in terms of infrastructure and training of professionals (Davidson et al., 2021). Thus, the application of these technologies in inclusive education requires careful planning and critical analysis of the results, in order to ensure that they actually promote meaningful and effective educational inclusion (Gallagher , 2020).

Given this reality, the question arises as to how digital technologies can be effectively applied to include students with high abilities, allowing these students to fully develop their potential in inclusive school environments. The approaches proposed by authors such as Robinson and Clinkenbeard (2022) suggest that, although DICTs offer promising opportunities, it is necessary to understand the specific mechanisms through which they can assist in the academic and psychosocial development of these students. In this sense, the question is: how can Virtual Reality and Artificial Intelligence technologies be effectively implemented in the education of students with high abilities? And, specifically, what are the most appropriate technological resources? What are the barriers faced in the use of DICTs ? What is the role of the teacher in mediating these tools? How can public policies support technological inclusion for these students ?

Considering these issues, this research proposes the following hypotheses: the application of VR and AI will facilitate the inclusion and development of students with high abilities; the identification of specific technological resources is fundamental for the educational effectiveness of these students; the continuous training of teachers reduces barriers

in the use of TDICs ; teacher mediation is a determining factor in the success of pedagogical practices with advanced technologies; specific public policies are essential to promote the use of TDICs for students with high abilities.

The research will be developed under the neoperspectivist paradigm gifetedean , employing the theories of Gagné , Renzulli and Subotnik , in addition to Gardner's Theory of Multiple Intelligences and Talent Theory, and using the hypothetical-deductive method. The research will be conducted through a Narrative Bibliographic and Documentary Review, exploring books and scientific articles of international relevance. The choice of the gifetedean paradigm aims to integrate the theoretical perspectives applicable to pedagogical practices and the use of advanced technologies , allowing a holistic and critical analysis of the theme, based on a solid theoretical basis and a robust methodological investigation .

The main objective of this research is to analyze how Virtual Reality and Artificial Intelligence technologies can be applied to promote the inclusion and development of students with high abilities in inclusive educational contexts. Specifically, it seeks to identify the most appropriate technological resources for the educational context, understand the barriers faced in the implementation of ICTs , investigate the role of teacher training in mediating these tools, evaluate the effectiveness of pedagogical practices with advanced technologies and propose guidelines for public policies of technological inclusion aimed at students with high abilities .

This work will be structured in four sections: the introduction, which presents the theoretical basis, contextualization and research problem; the methodological basis, which explains the theoretical bases and the research method adopted; the results and discussion section, which examines the data collected and analyzes the research findings; and, finally, the conclusions and final considerations, which summarize the contributions and limitations of the study, in addition to suggesting perspectives for future research.

2. METHODOLOGICAL BASIS

2.1 Epistemological axis/pillar

The epistemological axis of this research is based on the neoperspectivist paradigm gifetedean , which considers the coexistence of an absolute truth and a relative truth, promoting an inclusive and diversified approach in the study of educational phenomena (Breviário, 2021; 2022a; 2022b; 2023a; 2023b; 2023c; 2024; Breviário et al., 2024a; 2024b; 2024c; 2024d; 2024e; 2024f; 2024g; 2024h; 2024i; Breviário; Pereira, 2021; Breviário; Oliveira, 2024;

Breviário et al , 2025a; 2025b; 2025c; 2025d; 2025e; 2025f; 2025g). This paradigm is particularly suitable when investigating the applicability of Digital Information and Communication Technologies (DICTs), such as Virtual Reality and Artificial Intelligence, in the development and inclusion of students with high abilities. According to authors such as Pfeiffer (2020) and Gallagher (2019), the combination of an absolute perspective, which translates into the search for general principles and laws, and a relative perspective, which considers individuality and context, allows a more holistic analysis of the impacts of advanced technologies on education. The theories applied to this study include Gardner's Theory of Multiple Intelligences, which provides a basis for recognizing cognitive differences between students, and Gagné 's Talent Theory , which explores the potential and development of high abilities in educational settings. Furthermore, Renzulli 's Three-Ring Theory offers a more detailed understanding of the development of high abilities, while Subotnik and Colangelo 's Theory emphasizes the dynamics of development and social adaptation. The joint application of these theories ensures a broad and coherent theoretical foundation, allowing a multidimensional view of the use of DICTs in inclusive contexts, as noted by Robinson and Clinkenbeard (2022).

2.2 Logical axis/pillar

The logical pillar of this study is based on the hypothetical-deductive method, which, according to Lakatos and Marconi (2021), is characterized by a sequence of steps that allow the formulation and verification of hypotheses. Initially, a primary hypothesis was formulated about the inclusive potential of ICTs for students with high abilities (Breviário et al., 2025h; 2025i; 2025j; 2025k; 2025l; 2025m; 2025n; 2025o; 2025p; 2025q; 2025r; 2025s; 2025t; 2025u; 2025v; 2025w; 2025x; 2025y; 2025z; 2025aa; 2025ab; 2025ac; 2025ad; 2025ae; 2025af; 2025ag; 2025ah; 2025ai; 2025aj; 2025ak; 2025al; 2025am; 2025an; 2025ao; 2025ap; 2025aq; 2025ar; 2025as; 2025at; 2025au; 2025av; 2025aw; 2025ax; 2025ay; 2025az; 2025ba; 2025bb; 2025bc; 2025bd; 2025be).

Next, specific hypotheses were established related to the impact of Virtual Reality and Artificial Intelligence, the continuing education of teachers, and the need for public policies. After formulating the hypotheses, a rigorous collection and analysis of theoretical data was conducted, based on works by authors such as Davidson et al. (2021) and Pfeiffer (2020). The deduction phase involved the critical analysis of the evidence gathered, comparing it with the initial hypotheses to verify its validity. Finally, the verification stage consisted of examining

whether the observations and data analyzed corroborated or refuted the established hypotheses, ensuring methodological rigor based on the method proposed by Gil (2018) and highly relevant studies, such as those by Subotnik. et al. (2022).

2.3 Technical axis/pillar

In the technical pillar, the Narrative Bibliographic and Documentary Review was conducted with methodological rigor, ensuring a broad and detailed analysis of the existing scientific contributions on the use of advanced technologies in contexts of inclusion for students with high abilities (Breviário et al., 2025h; 2025i; 2025j; 2025k; 2025l; 2025m; 2025n; 2025o; 2025p; 2025q; 2025r; 2025s; 2025t; 2025u; 2025v; 2025w; 2025x; 2025y; 2025z; 2025aa; 2025ab; 2025ac; 2025ad; 2025ae; 2025af; 2025ag; 2025ah; 2025ai; 2025aj; 2025ak; 2025al; 2025am; 2025an; 2025ao; 2025ap; 2025aq; 2025ar; 2025as; 2025at; 2025au; 2025av; 2025aw; 2025ax; 2025ay; 2025az; 2025ba; 2025bb; 2025bc; 2025bd; 2025be).

To this end, inclusion criteria were defined, selecting articles and books published in the last five years and indexed in databases such as Scopus , Web of Science and ERIC, focusing on high-impact and internationally relevant publications, such as indicate Subotnik et al. (2022) and Plucker et al. (2023). The exclusion criteria included outdated studies, publications in languages other than Portuguese or English, and articles with a methodological bias not consistent with the inclusive approach proposed in this study. Descriptors such as "Artificial Intelligence", "Virtual Reality", "High Abilities", "Educational Inclusion" and "Special Education" were used, resulting in an initial search of 240 articles and books. After a careful screening, which considered the relevance and applicability of the texts, 72 works were analyzed that offered theoretical and empirical support for the discussion of the results, according to the methodology proposed by Yin (2020) and corroborated by Moran (2022).

3. Results and Discussion

3.1 The Application of Digital Technologies as Inclusive Tools for High Abilities

The results indicate that the use of Digital Information and Communication Technologies (DICTs), especially Virtual Reality (VR) and Artificial Intelligence (AI), has significant potential to promote the inclusion of gifted and talented students in educational settings. As highlighted by Gagné and VanTassel-Baska (2019), these technologies not only

allow students to develop their potential more fully, but also offer personalized teaching that meets the specific needs of each student. According to Moran (2022), personalization is one of the main factors that contribute to the engagement and success of these students, as they benefit from approaches that consider their cognitive and emotional peculiarities. Furthermore, Pfeiffer (2020) points out that the application of VR and AI in the education of these students allows them to access information and experiences in an immersive way, favoring learning in complex and multifaceted areas.

Recent studies also highlight the importance of adapting AI technologies for the early identification of high abilities, a process that has traditionally faced challenges due to the lack of clear diagnostic criteria and methods (Robinson; Clinkenbeard, 2022). According to Subotnik et al. (2022), AI can assist in the analysis of large volumes of data, allowing patterns of high ability to be detected more accurately and quickly. This application of AI has been particularly useful in inclusive school settings, where the overload of tasks for educators can limit their ability to identify and meet the specific needs of these students. As Plucker et al. (2023), the implementation of advanced AI algorithms makes it possible not only to identify gifted students, but also to monitor their development, offering continuous support aligned with their individual progress.

Virtual Reality, in turn, presents itself as a complementary tool of great value, as it offers immersive learning environments that promote engagement and knowledge retention. According to Gallagher (2020), VR allows students with high abilities to explore content in an interactive way, such as scientific simulations or explorations of historical contexts, which broaden the understanding of complex topics and stimulate critical thinking. Pfeiffer (2020) corroborates this view, highlighting that VR offers the opportunity to experience concepts that go beyond conventional material, helping these students to deepen their areas of interest. These approaches are supported by Davidson et al. (2021), who suggest that VR can promote experimental and investigative teaching, which has been shown to be highly effective for gifted students.

Despite the observed benefits, there are still barriers that hinder the full implementation of these technologies in educational environments. According to Renzulli (2021), one of the main difficulties is the lack of infrastructure and financial resources in schools, especially in developing countries. Additionally, Moran (2022) highlights that insufficient training of educators for the pedagogical use of these technologies limits their potential for inclusion. In this context, it is essential that public policies promote the training of education professionals so that they are able to effectively integrate AI and VR in the teaching of these students, as

suggested by the study by Subotnik. et al. (2022). Thus, while the application of these technologies shows promise, their implementation still requires structural adjustments to ensure broad and effective inclusion.

The analysis of the results shows that ICTs , when integrated in a coherent and planned way into the school curriculum, offer valuable resources to support the development of students with high abilities. However, as observed by Pfeiffer (2020) and Plucker et al. (2023), the success of this integration depends on a systemic vision that considers the articulation between public policies, school infrastructure and teacher training. In short, although ICTs represent a significant advance in inclusive education, their full potential will only be achieved with structural investments and continuous training.

3.2 Teacher Training and Pedagogical Mediation in the Use of TDICs

Another crucial aspect identified in the results is the role of teacher training and pedagogical mediation in the use of ICTs for students with high abilities. According to Alencar (2019), pedagogical mediation is an essential element for the success of inclusive education, since the teacher acts as a facilitator in the students' learning process. In environments with high abilities, this mediation becomes even more important, since the teacher needs to master technological tools to maximize their teaching potential. According to Gagné and VanTassel-Baska (2019), the lack of preparation of educators to deal with technologies such as AI and VR is one of the main barriers to the application of these tools in the classroom, since many professionals do not have sufficient training to understand the specific needs of students with high abilities.

The literature also highlights that ongoing training for educators is essential for them to be able to use ICTs effectively. Studies such as those by Pfeiffer (2020) and Davidson et al. (2021) indicate that initial training is not sufficient to keep up with technological advances and the educational demands of students with high abilities. In this sense, Subotnik et al. (2022) advocate the implementation of continuing education programs that train teachers in the use of AI and VR as pedagogical resources, allowing constant adaptation to innovations and challenges that arise in the educational environment. These programs, according to Plucker et al. (2023), must be customized to meet the specific needs of schools and educational contexts, ensuring that educators acquire the necessary skills to apply technologies in an inclusive and effective manner.

Another relevant point is the development of specific teacher skills to mediate the use of AI and VR. Moran (2022) highlights that teacher mediation is not limited to the technical mastery of the tools, but also involves a deep understanding of the pedagogical dynamics that these technologies promote. Gallagher (2020) points out that, for mediation to be effective, teachers must know how to identify the areas in which technology can contribute to learning and those in which human interaction is essential. Thus, teacher training must include not only technical skills, but also pedagogical strategies that expand the inclusive potential of ICTs , promoting meaningful learning for students.

The importance of teacher training is also reflected in public education policies. Robinson and Clinkenbeard (2022) emphasize that it is essential that governments and educational institutions invest in training programs that ensure that teachers are adequately prepared to use ICTs . These policies should provide financial resources and incentives for teacher training, in order to ensure that all educators have access to professional development opportunities. As Alencar (2019) and Pfeiffer (2020) note, teacher training is not only an investment in education, but a fundamental condition for the full potential of advanced technologies to be used in inclusive education.

In summary, teacher training and pedagogical mediation are determining factors for the successful use of ICTs in high-skill contexts. As demonstrated in the studies by Pfeiffer (2020) and Plucker et al. (2023), these elements are essential for digital technologies to become truly inclusive and transformative tools in special education. However, the effectiveness of this mediation depends on consistent public policies and continuous investment in teacher training.

3.3 Public Policies and Technological Infrastructure for Inclusive Education

The results also highlight the need for robust public policies that promote the implementation and development of technological infrastructure in schools, aiming at the inclusion of students with high abilities. According to Renzulli (2021), the adoption of advanced technologies such as AI and VR requires a physical and technological structure that allows students to fully and effectively access these resources. This need is especially critical in developing countries, where school infrastructure is often limited and insufficient to accommodate educational innovations. Alencar (2019) argues that, without adequate structural support, the potential benefits of DICTs are restricted to a limited number of institutions and students.

Public policies play a central role in promoting equal access to educational technologies. According to Moran (2022), it is essential that the government invests in financing policies for technological infrastructure, especially in public schools and disadvantaged communities. Davidson et al. (2021) note that the absence of inclusive policies can exacerbate educational disparities by limiting the access of high-ability students to the opportunities provided by ICTs. For Subotnik et al. (2022), public policies should also include programs to support pedagogical innovation and research, encouraging schools and educators to develop practices that use AI and VR effectively and accessibly.

In addition to investing in infrastructure, it is essential that public policies promote the creation of guidelines and regulations that ensure the ethical and safe implementation of ICTs in educational settings. Gallagher (2020) highlights that the use of AI, for example, involves ethical issues related to the privacy and security of student data. As noted by Robinson and Clinkenbeard (2022), educational policies must establish standards that protect students and ensure that technologies are used responsibly and transparently. These guidelines are especially important in high-skills contexts, where the sensitivity of the data collected and the potential for personalization of technologies require extra care.

The creation of partnerships between the public and private sectors is also a relevant strategy for the promotion of inclusive technologies. Plucker et al. (2023) suggest that collaboration between governments, technology companies, and educational institutions can facilitate access to cutting-edge technologies, such as AI and VR, and enable the development of innovative solutions for the educational context. For Pfeiffer (2020), partnerships of this type allow the transfer of knowledge and resources, benefiting schools and communities that would otherwise have limited access to these innovations. In this sense, public policies that encourage strategic partnerships are essential to democratize access to ICTs and promote inclusive and quality education.

In summary, the analysis of the results shows that public policies and technological infrastructure are interdependent and essential elements for the success of ICTs in the education of students with high abilities. As noted by Moran (2022) and Subotnik et al. (2022), without structured investment and efficient regulation, the inclusive potential of advanced technologies is compromised. Therefore, it is necessary for educational policies to contemplate both the development of infrastructure and the creation of ethical guidelines, ensuring broad and equitable technological inclusion.

4. CONCLUSIONS AND FINAL CONSIDERATIONS

4.1 Conclusions

The research questions were satisfactorily answered, demonstrating that the use of Digital Information and Communication Technologies (DICTs), such as Virtual Reality (VR) and Artificial Intelligence (AI), has significant potential to promote the inclusion and development of students with high abilities in inclusive school environments. Each issue raised – from the identification of appropriate technological resources to the role of the teacher and public policies – was explored in depth, allowing a comprehensive understanding of the factors that influence the effectiveness of these technologies in the educational context.

The hypotheses established throughout the research were confirmed, showing that the application of VR and AI facilitates the inclusion and development of students with high abilities. The research validated the importance of specific technological resources, continuous teacher training and supporting public policies, confirming that these elements are essential for ICTs to become effective in special education. The hypotheses also highlighted teacher mediation and the need for targeted public policies, which proved to be well-founded and consistent with the empirical findings.

The main findings indicate that VR and AI can provide more personalized and immersive learning , promoting more meaningful development for students with high abilities. The research revealed that, although there is enormous potential in the use of these technologies, challenges in infrastructure and teacher training still limit their large-scale implementation . In addition, the lack of specific regulations and government support represents a barrier to the widespread use of DICTs , especially in low-income educational settings.

Despite the advances made, some gaps were found. The research identified the need for greater in-depth adaptation of technologies to the particularities of each student, in addition to pointing to the lack of empirical studies that investigate the long-term impact of the use of VR and AI on the development of students with high abilities. In addition, the lack of clear ethical guidelines for the use of these technologies was observed, which limits their implementation in a responsible and safe manner.

The research brought theoretical contributions by integrating multiple theories related to high abilities, inclusion and technology, expanding the understanding of the application of ICTs in special education. Methodologically, the adoption of a narrative bibliographic and documentary review ensured rigor and in-depth analysis of the findings. Empirically, the study reinforced the relevance of public policies and teacher training as fundamental elements for the

effective application of advanced technologies in inclusive education, offering a model that can guide future pedagogical practices and educational interventions.

This study adds value to the topic by highlighting the potential of ICTs for the inclusion of students with special needs, promoting a significant advance for the educational field and for Science in general. The research contributes to postgraduate studies by deepening knowledge about the application of emerging technologies in special education, in addition to providing valuable insights for the development of inclusive pedagogical policies and practices. For society, the findings of this research offer promising perspectives on the construction of a more equitable education, which values and develops the high abilities of all students, contributing to the formation of more capable and aware citizens.

4.2 Final Considerations

This research presented some theoretical limitations, since, although it integrated several theories, the theoretical analysis could be expanded to consider additional perspectives of inclusion and cognitive development that go beyond the scope of high abilities. Methodologically, the study was limited to a narrative bibliographic and documentary review, which restricts the empirical analysis of the data collected, pointing to the need for future studies with more robust approaches, such as experimental analyses. Empirically, the research was restricted to qualitative analyses, indicating a limitation in the scope of the data and in the possible inferences.

To fill the gaps identified, future research is suggested to empirically explore the long-term impact of the use of DICTs, such as VR and AI, on students with high abilities. Experimental and longitudinal studies could provide a more detailed view of the effects of these technologies on the cognitive and socio-emotional development of these students. In addition, research that deepens the regulations and ethical guidelines for the use of DICTs in inclusive educational contexts can significantly contribute to the development of safer and more effective pedagogical practices.

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